

Statistical optimization of the culture conditions for L-glutamic acid production by a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀

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Abstract: Statistical optimization for L-glutamic acid production by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ was carried out using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) emphasizing Central Composite Design (CCD) with different variables. Maximum production of L-glutamic acid (mg/ml) was obtained with 72 h of incubation period.

Keywords: Statistical, optimization, L-glutamic acid, Response Surface Methodology (RSM), Central Composite Design (CCD).

Introduction

Micrococcus glutamicus is a Gram-positive soil bacterium, widely used for L-amino acid fermentation since 1957¹. The ability of the bacterium to accumulate L-amino acids results from multiple improvements made through repeated random mutations followed by selection^{2,3}. L-Glutamic acid has a wide spectrum of use in food additives, feed supplements, agrochemicals, cosmetic industries etc.⁴. Owing to the improvements of industrial fermentation process, many efforts were focused on to improve L-glutamic acid fermentation, especially from the standpoint of savings and production cost⁵⁻⁷. Fermentation is a function of different physico-chemical factors to which a bacterium has to expose which influence the productivity as a specific bacterium has a definite range of culture conditions for optimum productivity⁴.

Statistical optimization of biological processes cover the optimization of different parameters of bioprocesses devoting much required attention to the experimental optimization using statistical tools. It also examines the complexity of the nature of bio-

logical processes, the requirements for optimal and rationale of statistical and non-statistical optimization processes. Statistical methods of optimization of fermentation conditions are widely used nowadays as these methods require less number of experimental set up and provide a suitable understanding of the interactions among different physico-chemical factors governing the fermentative outcome⁸. Commonly Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is used for this purpose. Adinaryana and Elliaiah (2002) used it for alkaline protease production by *Bacillus* sp⁹. Nelofer *et al.* (2008) applied RSM for optimization of ϵ -lysine production by *Corynebacterium glutamicum*¹⁰. Recently, Ganguly and Satapathy (2017) used RSM to optimize the culture conditions for L-methionine production by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X300¹¹.

In this present study, RSM has been chosen for the statistical optimization of L-glutamic acid production by the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀. This study also intended how to successfully apply mathematical and statistical tools to optimize the fermentation process.

Materials and methods:

Microorganism : *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ was developed by induced mutantion and protoplast fusion was used throughout the study¹².

Composition of growth medium: Glucose, 20 g; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 1.6 g; NaCl, 2.5 g; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.25 g; MnSO₄.4H₂O, 0.1 g; K₂HPO₄, 1 g; KH₂PO₄, 1 g; H₂O, 1 L and agar, 2% as a solidifying agent¹¹.

Growth conditions: The fermentation was carried out using medium volume, 30 ml; initial pH 7; shaker speed, 200 rpm; the age of inoculum, 48 h; cell density, 6 × 10⁶ cells/ml and temperature, 30°C¹².

Composition of basal salt medium for L-glutamic acid production: L-Glutamic acid production was initially carried out (before optimization) using the following basal salt medium: glucose, 60 g; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 1.5 g; K₂HPO₄, 1.4 g; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.9 g; FeSO₄.7H₂O, 0.01 g; biotin, 60 µg and H₂O, 1 L¹¹.

Analysis of L-glutamic acid: Descending paper chromatography was employed for detecting L-glutamic acid in the broth and was run for 18 h on Whatman No. 1 chromatography paper. Solvent system contained: n-butanol:acetic acid:water (2:1:1). The spot was visualized by spraying a solution of 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone and quantitative estimation of L-glutamic acid in the suspension was done using a colorimetric method¹².

Confirmatory test for L-glutamic acid: Quantitative determination of L-glutamic acid in the fermentation medium without purification was done following the method as described by Greenstein and Wintz (1996). 1 ml of 5 (N) NaOH, and 0.1 ml of 10% sodium nitroprusside solution, was added to 5 ml supernatant after centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 15 min. The tube was thoroughly shaken and the mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min. 25 ml of 3% aqueous solution of glycerine was added to the reaction mixture with frequent shaking over a period of 10 min. After additional 10 min interval, 2 ml of concentrated orthophosphoric acid was added drop

wise to the mixture and the test tube was properly shaken. Colour development was allowed to produce for 5 min and colour intensity was measured at 540 nm in spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 68 UV VIS). The L-glutamic acid yield was extrapolated from a standard L-glutamic acid curve⁷.

Estimation of dry cell weight (DCW): The cell paste was obtained from the fermentation broth by centrifugation and dried at 100°C until constant cell weight was obtained¹².

Statistical analysis: All data were expressed as mean ± SEM, where *n* = 6, where 'n' denotes the number of experimental set up. Data were analyzed by one way ANOVA using a software Prism 4.0, considering *p* < 0.05 as significant and *p* < 0.01 as highly significant¹¹.

Response Surface Methodology: It consists of a group of experimental technologies, used for evaluation of relationship between different variables and measured responses. Plackett-Burmann design was used to assess the pick variables that influence L-methionine fermentation by the mutant significantly and insignificant factors were eliminated in order to obtain a smaller manageable set of variables. RSM was applied in two stages, first to trace out the significant variables for the production using Plackett-Burmann design criterion and later significant variables related from Plackett-Burmann design were optimized by a central composite design. The experimental design and statistical analysis of the data were done by using software, Prism 4.0¹¹.

Plackett-Burmann Design (PBD): Each variable was examined at two levels, namely a high level (+1) and low level (-1). Initial pH, volume of medium, age of inoculum, shaker's speed, temperature, cell density, period of incubation, carbon source, nitrogen source, K₂HPO₄, KH₂PO₄, CaCO₃, MgSO₄.7H₂O, NaCl, KCl, ZnSO₄.7H₂O, Na₂MoO₄.2H₂O, MnSO₄.4H₂O, FeSO₄.7H₂O, biotin and thiamine-HCl were screened by conducting six experiments using Plackett-Burmann design. All

experiments were conducted in six sets and mean values of L-methionine production was used for statistical analysis. The variables, which were significant at 1% level ($p < 0.01$) from one way ANOVA were considered to have high impact on L-methionine production and were further optimized using Central Composite Design¹¹.

Central Composite Design (CCD): It was applied to determine the optimum levels of seven significant production parameters determined from PBD. The effects of the parameters (namely: age of inoculums, shaker's speed, temperature, cell density, glucose concentration, nitrogen concentration, K_2HPO_4 , KH_2PO_4 , $CaCO_3$, $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and biotin) on L-methionine production by the mutant were examined at levels: -2, -1, 0, +1 and +2 where $\alpha + 2^{n/4}$, where ' $\alpha +$ ' represents the number of levels of significance considered (i.e. 5). Hence ' n ' was the number of variables and '0' corresponded to the central point. The level of each variable was determined by the following equation :

Coded value =

$$2 \times \frac{\text{Actual level} - \text{Highest level}}{\text{Highest level} - \text{lowest level}} \quad (1)$$

The experimental plan and the following independent variable were obtained from CCD: volume of medium, (15–35 ml), initial pH (6–8), age of inoculum (24–84), cell density (1×10^8 – 6×10^8 cells), temperature (25–32°C), period of incubation (24–108 h), carbon sources (glucose, fructose, sucrose, lactose, maltose, ribose, xylose, starch, dextrin, sodium citrate, sodium acetate and glycerol), different concentrations of glucose (20–140 g/L), nitrogen sources (urea, ammonium sulphate, sodium nitrate, ammonium chloride, ammonium nitrate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, ammonium dihydrogen phosphate, ammonium carbonate, ammonium oxalate and ammonium citrate) and different concentrations of nitrogen (1–10 g/L) in the form of ammonium sulphate.

After identification of significant variables using Plackett-Burmann design, Box-Wilson 2^4 factorial CCD was applied to optimize these variables. Five levels of variables were coded as:

$$Z = (X - X')/d_o^x \quad (2)$$

where Z = code value; X = natural value; X' = natural value in central domain; d_o^x = increment of X corresponding to one unit of Z .

A total number of 31 experiments with 8 axial points ($\alpha = 2$) and six replications was applied for Box-Wilson 2^4 factorial CCD. The general form of the second degree polynomial equation was applied in this present study. The equation can be presented as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (3)$$

where, Y = response variable; β_0 = coefficient of interaction effect (offset term); β_i = linear coefficient (i-th term); β_{ii} = coefficient of quadratic effect (ii-th term); β_{ij} = interaction coefficient (ij-th term)¹¹.

Results

*Screening of variables by Plackett-Burmann design criterion for L-glutamic acid production by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀:*

The variables which significantly alter the production of L-glutamic acid by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ were examined by Plackett-Burmann design. All the twenty one parameters such as volume of medium, initial pH, age of inoculums, shaker's speed, temperature, cell density, the period of incubation, glucose concentration, nitrogen concentration (in term of ammonium sulphate), K_2HPO_4 , KH_2PO_4 , $CaCO_3$, $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $NaCl$, KCl , $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $Na_2MoO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$, $MnSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$, biotin and thiamine-HCl were assessed at two widely spaced levels (Table 1).

Among the twenty one variables studied, shaker's speed (III), age of inoculum (IV), cell density (V), temperature (VI), glucose concentration (VIII), nitrogen concentration (IX), K_2HPO_4 (X), KH_2PO_4

Table 1. Level of variables examined for L-glutamic acid production by the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ using Plackett-Burmann design criterion

Code	Parameter	High level (+1)		Low level (-1)	
		Level	Activity (mg/ml)	Level	Activity (mg/ml)
I	Volume of medium (ml)	25	6.1±0.161	13	8.2±0.771
II	Initial pH	7.0	8.2±0.662	8	7.4±0.661
III	Shaker's speed (rpm)	200	8.1±0.662	98	9.8±0.662
IV	Age of inoculum (h)	72	6.2±0.531	22	7.2±0.721
V	Cell density (cells)	6×10 ⁶	10.7±0.771	1×10 ⁶	5.1±0.613
VI	Temperature (°C)	28	7.3±0.791	24	6.3±0.621
VII	The period of incubation (h)	84	6.3±0.779	24	2.1±0.882
VIII	Glucose concentration (g/L)	120	16.8±0.771	20	8.3±0.771
IX	Nitrogen content (g/L)	8.0	21.3±2.321	2.0	13.6±0.772
X	K ₂ HPO ₄ (g/L)	2.1	24.2±1.713	2.0	22.1±1.773
XI	KH ₂ PO ₄ (g/L)	2.3	38.2±0.719	0.0	23.2±0.771
XII	CaCO ₃ (g/L)	4.1	36.2±0.711	0.0	32.2±0.513
XIII	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (g/L)	2.3	24.2±1.311	0.2	24.2±0.614
XIV	NaCl (g/L)	2.2	37.3±0.771	2.0	40.6±0.316
XV	KCl (g/L)	2.8	38.2±0.611	2.0	39.6±0.773
XVI	FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (mg/L)	35	20.6±0.773	6.1	22.4±1.771
XVII	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (mg/L)	1.4	39.1±0.661	0.0	39.3±0.221
XVIII	Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O (mg/L)	7.3	40.3±0.668	0.0	33.1±0.792
XIX	MnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O (mg/L)	5.5	42.4±0.712	0.0	40.3±0.412
XX	Biotin (µg/ml)	80	52.1±0.771	0.0	42.2±0.513
XXI	Thiamine-HCl (µg/ml)	80	50.3±0.772	0.0	51.6±0.772

(XI), CaCO₃ (XII), MgSO₄·7H₂O (XIII), KCl (XV), FeSO₄·7H₂O (XVI), MnSO₄·4H₂O (XIX) and biotin (XX) had significant ($p < 0.01$) effect of L-glutamic acid fermentation by the mutant, which was obtained from one way ANOVA. The coefficient of determinant (R^2) of the model obtained from regression analysis was 0.861, suggesting thereby the model could explain up to 86.1% variation of the data. Thus the production of L-glutamic acid by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ using Plackett-Burman design showed wide range of variations which implied that it required further optimization.

Application of Box-Wilson central composite design for the optimization of L-glutamic acid production by Micrococcus glutamicus AB₁₀₀:

The optimum level of the key variables and the effect of their interactions on L-glutamic acid pro-

duction by the mutant were further examined using Central Composite Design (CCD) of RSM.

The first CCD:

The fermentation trials for L-glutamic acid by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ were examined by CCD using the following variables : shaker's speed (III), age of inoculum (IV), cell density (V), temperature (VI), glucose concentration (VIII), nitrogen concentration (IX), K₂HPO₄ (X), KH₂PO₄ (XI), CaCO₃ (XII), MgSO₄·7H₂O (XIII), KCl (XV), FeSO₄·7H₂O (XVI), MnSO₄·4H₂O (XIX) and biotin (XX). The highest level of L-methionine was obtained up to 52.1 mg/ml with a biomass of 28.5 mg/ml and residual sugar content of 23.8%. Table 2 depicted the results of the second order Response Surface Models for L-glutamic acid production by the mutant, obtained by one way ANOVA.

Table 2. One way ANOVA for full quadratic model used for L-glutamic acid production by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀

Source	Degree of freedom (df)	Sum of square	Mean square	F-Value	Probe > F
Model	78.261	6	6.713	11.731	0.0011
Residual	6.226	3	0.611	12.116	0.0214
Lack of fit	65.332	4	0.221	14.662	0.0441
Pure error	0.313	4	0.042	20.312	0.03123
Total	90.224				

$R^2 = 0.8132$

'F' was named after Sir Ronald Fisher.

Table 3. L-Glutamic acid production by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ using significant physical parameters based on CCD

Trial	Factor				L-Glutamic acid (mg/ml) [mean ± SEM]	Predicted value (mg/ml)	Residual values (mg/ml)
	X3	X4	X5	X6			
1	100	48	7×10 ⁶	31	12.8±0.713	8.5	5.1
2	150	24	2×10 ⁶	28	11.8±0.713	11.3	2.1
3	150	72	3×10 ⁶	25	11.3±0.682	6.8	2.9
4	100	60	4×10 ⁶	32	12.3±0.813	8.9	3.1
5	100	36	3×10 ⁶	28	12.3±0.813	7.9	5.1
6	200	84	4×10 ⁶	28	12.2±0.774	8.1	3.1
7	150	60	4×10 ⁶	27	12.1±0.668	6.1	5.9
8	200	48	5×10 ⁶	26	11.6±0.817	7.3	3.9
9	100	48	4×10 ⁶	30	13.9±0.691	9.1	7.1
10	100	24	5×10 ⁶	29	14.1±0.682	9.7	6.1
11	150	72	7×10 ⁶	32	14.8±0.661	7.4	6.9
12	300	60	4×10 ⁶	31	12.9±0.872	7.7	6.1
13	150	84	3×10 ⁶	31	12.4±0.771	7.9	6.4
14	100	72	2×10 ⁶	25	12.4±0.711	6.4	4.2
15	300	72	3×10 ⁶	29	12.8±0.771	5.2	5.5
16	300	84	5×10 ⁶	60	12.6±0.652	8.3	3.2
17	200	84	4×10 ⁶	60	12.8±0.719	11.1	2.9
18	200	72	3×10 ⁶	48	12.9±0.691	8.9	3.9
19	300	48	6×10 ⁶	96	11.1±0.778	9.1	2.4
20	150	60	4×10 ⁶	96	12.4±0.662	6.4	4.8
21	100	48	2×10 ⁶	26	12.8±0.828	9.8	2.6
22	300	48	3×10 ⁶	30	12.8±0.877	11.8	3.8
23	150	60	5×10 ⁶	30	11.9±0.613	11.3	2.8
24	300	60	4×10 ⁶	28	12.8±0.613	6.8	7.3
25	200	72	6×10 ⁶	28	12.8±0.816	8.7	6.4
26	200	84	5×10 ⁶	25	11.8±0.691	8.4	3.3
27	200	84	6×10 ⁶	26	12.3±0.661	9.4	3.1
28	300	48	4×10 ⁶	25	12.6±0.618	11.1	3.3
29	200	48	4×10 ⁶	26	12.1±0.618	8.1	2.1
30	300	60	6×10 ⁶	26	11.3±0.629	7.1	3.9
31	200	72	2×10 ⁶	30	12.1±0.518	7.9	4.1
32	250	48	2×10 ⁶	28	12.1±0.718	7.2	4.2

Chi square test with a very low probability value ($\alpha < 0.001$) indicated that the model was highly significant. R^2 (0.982) indicated that the sample variance in L-glutamic acid production of 93.6% was attributed to the independent variables and only 2.1% of total variation cannot be justified by the model.

All total 32 experimental trials for both physical and nutritional variables were examined for the estimation of the principal effects and multi-factors interactions. The production of L-glutamic acid was increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) after optimization of nutritional parameters compared to the optimization of physical parameters.

Table 4. L-Glutamic acid production by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ using significant nutritional parameters based on CCD

Trial	Factor										L-Glutamic acid (mg/ml)	Predicted value (mg/ml)	Residual value (mg/ml)
	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XV	XVI	XIX	XX			
1	30	4.1	2.2	2.3	3.1	2.4	0.8	30	1.0	0.0	44.3±0.721	41.6	2.3
2	20	10	2.5	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.2	6.0	1.4	60	44.2±0.613	34.8	3.9
3	140	6.1	2.2	0.0	1.3	0.8	2.1	20	5.1	2.2	34.6±0.614	33.1	6.2
4	40	6.1	1.2	1.6	2.2	0.6	0.0	35	2.8	1.3	46.8±0.832	44.2	6.2
5	60	1.2	2.1	1.2	2.7	1.4	2.2	20	2.4	4.3	50.6±0.884	40.3	6.2
6	40	1.2	2.1	2.4	3.3	0.6	2.1	35	3.2	4.2	52.1±0.651	44.2	3.9
7	60	1.1	2.6	1.3	3.1	0.8	1.2	5.2	3.1	3.4	44.2±0.611	41.2	4.1
8	120	2.2	2.1	1.4	1.6	0.8	1.6	5.5	3.6	3.3	44.3±0.661	40.1	5.4
9	80	1.3	2.5	1.4	1.2	1.1	1.3	10	2.2	6.5	51.4±0.661	43.1	3.1
10	40	2.2	2.1	2.5	2.2	1.4	1.3	20	4.1	4.4	40.2±0.612	40.1	5.0
11	120	1.2	1.2	1.4	1.3	1.1	1.1	20	0.0	3.6	30.1±0.811	24.5	3.3
12	140	4.2	1.4	1.3	0.0	1.2	1.7	10	2.4	3.1	41.2±0.691	34.2	3.1
13	40	1.0	1.3	1.4	2.3	1.6	0.0	35	2.2	0.0	34.1±0.513	30.4	4.1
14	40	1.2	1.6	0.0	1.2	0.8	0.2	25	2.2	0.0	40.1±0.613	33.5	2.1
15	60	4.1	2.4	0.0	2.4	0.7	0.0	25	4.4	20	42.1±0.615	40.1	4.1
16	80	1.2	2.6	1.2	1.1	0.6	0.0	10	6.2	5.7	41.6±0.829	41.8	5.1
17	120	1.3	2.8	1.4	1.3	0.7	0.0	10	6.3	3.3	40.8±0.638	33.8	3.3
18	60	6.3	2.8	1.3	1.2	0.8	2.4	10	4.4	4.2	44.8±0.613	40.3	3.6
19	100	7.4	1.6	2.6	3.3	0.4	2.7	10	4.4	4.8	43.9±0.813	40.6	3.6
20	140	1.4	1.6	2.2	3.3	1.4	1.4	5.7	2.3	4.3	41.4±0.613	40.2	3.6
21	100	1.2	2.8	0.0	3.6	1.2	1.1	5.2	4.6	4.1	52.6±0.613	40.5	4.2
22	120	8.7	1.2	0.0	2.2	1.3	1.3	5.5	2.1	3.3	41.1±0.619	33.8	2.1
23	120	1.1	1.6	0.0	0.0	1.4	1.1	20	4.3	3.6	44.6±0.639	40.1	4.1
24	140	8.3	1.4	1.2	1.5	1.2	1.1	25	6.3	4.2	41.2±0.832	40.3	3.8
25	60	1.3	1.8	1.4	1.3	1.1	1.7	20	6.2	4.8	51.6±0.471	44.8	3.3
26	60	1.2	1.5	1.6	2.2	1.1	1.5	20	2.4	3.2	34.3±0.811	33.4	2.2
27	80	1.4	2.6	2.1	2.4	2.1	1.2	35	2.7	20	45.2±0.914	41.8	4.8
28	60	9.1	1.2	1.1	2.5	1.2	1.1	1.9	6.3	30	40.1±0.719	33.8	1.9
29	100	6.5	1.9	2.1	1.6	1.1	1.2	1.1	5.8	20	40.1±0.813	42.6	2.9
30	120	2.6	2.6	1.9	0.0	1.6	1.3	1.1	6.3	10	48.5±0.664	33.2	4.8
31	140	1.1	2.9	1.1	1.7	1.1	1.3	0.0	4.1	10	44.1±0.791	41.8	4.1
32	60	8.3	2.5	1.1	1.6	1.2	1.8	2.1	6.7	20	41.8±0.719	33.6	2.9

Table 5. Model coefficient calculated from linear regression for the assessment of the significance of the independent variables

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error of mean	Computed <i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -Value
Intercept	50.210	0.033	189.322	0.000
III	0.713	0.043	2.113	0.011
IV	0.317	0.061	6.913	0.048
V	0.491	0.051	3.619	0.382
VI	0.499	0.061	1.913	0.532
VIII	0.639	0.043	3.811	0.011
IX	0.591	0.055	5.913	0.286
X	0.295	0.063	4.913	0.419
XI	0.611	0.039	3.915	0.482
XII	0.619	0.049	12.519	0.049
XIII	0.491	0.044	16.139	0.291
XIV	-0.049	0.046	-4.839	0.007
XV	0.491	0.048	4.913	0.039
XVI	0.492	0.046	6.919	0.613
XIX	0.438	0.059	6.913	0.226
XX	0.539	0.079	3.919	0.691

The second CCD:

Table 6 depicted the second order CCD for L-glutamic acid production in the form of variance (ANOVA) for the quadratic model.

Discussion

Shih and Shen (2006) optimized poly ϵ -lysine production by *Streptomyces albulus* IFO 14147 by RSM to examine the effect of yeast extract, glucose, ammonium sulphate and initial pH by shake-flask fermentation. They obtained both the first order with the interaction model ($R^2 = 0.8730$) which was more adequate than the pure first order model ($R^2 = 0.9907$). They used CCD to optimize the medium composition. Their experimental data were shouted with a second-order polynomial equation by a multiple regression analysis. The determination of coefficient ($R^2 = 0.732$) and the Fisher's test (significant at upper 6%) indicated a good adequacy of the sec-

Table 6. One way ANOVA for Response Surface Quadratic Model for L-glutamic acid production by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀

Source of data	Sum of square	Degree of freedom (df)	Mean square	F-Value	<i>p</i> -Value > F
Model	0.683	3	0.914	1180.16	< 0.0004
III	0.591	4	0.618	117.43	0.0051
IV	0.591	7	0.614	66.32	< 0.0003
V	0.519	3	0.491	111.48	< 0.0002
VI	0.439	4	0.442	221.51	0.0017
VIII	0.491	2	0.218	411.29	< 0.0004
IX	0.291	2	0.181	441.32	0.0049
X	0.491	2	0.117	811.41	0.0018
XI	0.317	4	0.217	287.41	0.0031
XII	0.741	8	0.618	69.71	< 0.0006
XIII	0.551	3	0.491	221.11	0.0011
XV	0.532	4	0.287	314.27	0.0019
XVI	0.517	6	0.211	616.14	< 0.0005
XIX	0.311	3	0.316	41.41	< 0.0003
XX	0.417	2	0.311	211.17	0.0011
Residual	1.313	2	0.211	-	-
Pure error	0.000	5	0.000	-	-
Lack of fit	2.131	2	0.437	-	-
Total	11.49				

$R^2 = 0.9838$, Adj $R^2 = 0.618$

'*R*' stands for regression; '*p*' stands for probability of getting or rejecting null hypothesis.

ond-order polynomial model used to analyze the data¹³. Nilofer *et al.* (2008) applied RSM to optimize the variables of L-lysine fermentation by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* AEC-2 using Plackett-Burman design and obtained four variables (the level of sugar in molasses, ammonium sulphate, and incubation temperature and inoculum size) were proved to be significant for L-lysine production. Furthermore, CCD (2⁴ factorial) was applied to determine the optimum levels of significant variables. A second order polynomial regression model was applied to explain the experimental data. Using these models, the production of L-lysine was increased up to 2.6 fold¹⁰. Pandey and Banik (2010) optimized six factors (namely : pH, temperature, fermentation time, orbital speed, age of inoculum and inoculum volume) for alkaline phosphate production by *Bacillus licheniformis* using RSM and reported that pH, temperature, fermentation time and orbital speed were significant ($p < 0.05$) using Plackett-Burman design methodology. An increase up to 1.8 fold in the production was obtained after optimization of the production using RSM¹⁴. Shankar *et al.* (2013) investigated the invertase production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* MK. The optimum levels of the key variables (orange peel, yeast extract and L-methionine) were used to determine their interactions on the production using CCD and RSM. The determined coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.8871$) was nearer to 1 which satisfied the adjustment of the quadratic model to the experimental data⁸. Patel *et al.* (2016) compared between one at a time variation factors and CCD for the accumulation of mycophenolic acid by *Penicillium brevicompactum* MTCC8010 in a 12 day batch culture. The medium optimization using one-at-a-time variation gave greater titer (8 fold), where as CCD

gave almost 5 fold greater titer compare to the production prior to the optimization¹⁵.

Conclusion

Among 32 experimental trials for examining the principal effects and multi-factors interactions revealed that the production of L-glutamic acid by the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ was increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 6.1 mg/ml to 51.4 mg/ml.

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